

Observation Guide

Researcher:

- Hello, my name is <researcher> and the goal of this meeting is to find problems and possible solutions in your Micro Frontends (MFE) architecture by detecting MFE anti-patterns (AP) in the MFEs your team is responsible for. You can also detect AP related to MFEs from other teams.
- You can check the existing AP by consulting a catalog of MFE AP available at <https://mfe-anti-patterns.online/micro-frontends-anti-patterns/#/catalog>
- Feel free to discuss problems that are not catalogued in an AP and propose solutions to them.
- You can register all detected AP and problems in the sheet I have shared with you, where you identify the detected AP (if so), describe the specific problem, propose a possible solution, identify an artifact or evidence of the problem (optional) and add general observations about the anti-pattern, problem, solution or other.
- This meeting will be recorded to enable further data analysis. Keep in mind that you are not being evaluated and you can conduct the problems identification anyway you want. All research with humans presents risks. In this study, participants will not incur any cost or burden for their participation and will not receive any form of reimbursement or compensation for taking part. You can withdraw from the study anytime. The main benefits are improving the overall quality of the system's architecture.
- Do you have any questions?

>>> Participant asks questions

Researcher:

- Therefore, now you can use the anti-patterns (or not) to identify problems and propose solutions anyway you want. If you have any questions, you can ask me.

>>> Participants identify problems until the final 5 minutes

Researcher:

- Since our meeting is ending, you can continue the problem identification and solution proposal by yourself. After one week, we will be in touch again so we can discuss the problems, solutions, and the anti-patterns identification process.
- You can continue fulfilling the detection form during this week and I will access it after our next meeting.
- Feel free to contact me in case of any doubts. Have a nice day!